

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/solmat

Erratum

Erratum to ‘Emissivity at high temperature of Ni-based superalloys for the design of solar receivers for future tower power plants’ [Solar Energy Mater. Solar Cells, 227, (2021), 111066]

Marianne Balat-Pichelin^{a,*}, Jean-Louis Sans^a, Eric Bêche^a, Ludovic Charpentier^a, Alain Ferrière^a, Sébastien Chomette^b

^a Laboratoire PROMES-CNRS, 7 rue du four solaire, 66120, Font-Romeu Odeillo, France

^b Université Grenoble Alpes, CEA, LITEN, 38000, Grenoble Cedex, France

The publisher regrets the incorrect writing of the two equations of section 2.2 about emissivity. The correct writing is the following:

“The direct method used at PROMES-CNRS laboratory is the one that corresponds directly to the definition of emissivity: the directional spectral radiance (L'_λ) of the material is measured as well as its temperature to calculate the spectral radiance of the blackbody (L_λ^0) at the same temperature [10–12]. The ratio of the radiances gives the spectral directional emissivity:

$$\varepsilon'_\lambda = L'_\lambda / L_\lambda^0$$

The corresponding hemispherical emissivity ε_λ^0 is then calculated by

integration of the directional values:

$$\varepsilon_\lambda^0 = \int_0^{\pi/2} \varepsilon'_\lambda \sin 2\theta d\theta$$

The instrument used for radiance measurement is a spectroradiometer that allows measurements at multiple discrete wavelengths, leading to a finer analysis of the behavior of materials, as for example during oxidation of alloys at high temperature.

The publisher would like to apologise for any inconvenience caused.

DOI of original article: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2021.111066>.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: Marianne.balat@promes.cnrs.fr (M. Balat-Pichelin).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2021.111228>